

Assessment of Socio-Economic Empowerment Using Information Communication and Technology Skills and Facilities among Secondary School Chemistry Teachers in North-West, Nigeria

Anaso, Joy N.¹

joyanaso@gmail.com

08039359656

¹Department of Chemistry, Federal University of Education, Zaria, Kaduna State, Nigeria

Abstract

The study investigated the Socio-Economic Empowerment using Information Communication and Technology skills and facilities among secondary school chemistry teachers in North-West, Nigeria in the use of Information Communication and Technology (ICT) skills and facilities. The study population consisted of seven hundred and twenty chemistry teachers drawn from eighty state government owned secondary schools in Kaduna and Kano States during the 2023/2024 academic session, the sample size of the study consisted of 120 chemistry teachers selected using purposive random sampling technique. The Research Design adopted for the study was survey method. Two research questions and two hypotheses guided the study. Descriptive statistics of mean (X), standard deviation (SD), were used to answer research questions while total weighted average response and one sample t- Test Statistics were used to test the hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance. The instrument for data collection was the researcher's structured questionnaire Chemistry Teachers Socio-Economic Empowerment Scale (CTSEES) and the instrument was validated by two computer experts and two chemistry lecturers from Science Education Department, Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria. Cronbach alpha was used to obtain a reliability coefficient of 0.78. The findings revealed that significant difference existed in the mean ratings of chemistry teachers on the development and provision of ICT facilities in secondary schools. It was recommended that policy-makers should ensure that functional ICT programmes are incorporated into the curriculum to help chemistry teachers actualize their potentials since skill acquisition is the best option for empowering chemistry teachers at the secondary school level.

Keywords: Socio-Economic Empowerment, Chemistry Teachers, Information Communication Technology

Introduction

It is important to understand the key concepts in this study: Socio-Economic Empowerment, Chemistry Teachers, and Information Communication Technology. Development is defined in different ways in various contexts – social, political, biological, scientific and technological. Generally, development is defined as a state in which things are improving. In the socio-economic context, development means the improvement of people's lifestyles through improved education and skills. It is the process of economic and social transformation based on cultural and environmental factors. Socio-economic development is therefore, the process of social and economic advancement in a society as well as a process of improvement in a variety of ways. It influences all aspects of human life in a country.

Socio-economy is defined by the Oxford Dictionary (2022) as relating to the interaction of social and economic factors while empowerment is to give authority or power and/or strength and confidence to the citizens. Empowerment, according to Rahman (2013) and Olomukoro (2016), is the process of awareness and capacity building leading to greater participation, greater decision making, power and control, and to transformative action. This term, therefore refers to measures designed to increase the degree of people's autonomy and self-determination in people to enable them represent their interests in a responsible and self-determined way, acting on their own authority. Empowerment as an action, refers both to the process of self-empowerment and to professional support of people. This enables them to overcome their sense of powerlessness and lack of influence; and to recognize and use their resources.

The term socio-economic empowerment is the process by which a nation improves the economic and social well-being of its people. A meaningful participation in development presupposes acquisition of knowledge and skills through literacy or education (Olomukoro, 2016). Education is therefore, the most effective instrument for socio-economic empowerment of teachers. Education is viewed as an instrument and a prime influencer of change conceived as development. High priority continues to be accorded to improve the educational status of teachers as they comprise the majority of the population in the country. To participate effectively and meaningfully in the developmental process, chemistry and other science teachers need to be empowered in all ramifications, especially in the socio-economic dimension. Literacy empowers and it is the most essential of all educational skills; teachers facilitate students' learning, raise their achievement level and improve their technological career aspiration. Udoh and Jacob (2016) also observed that the teacher is an effective and dominating factor

among the ones contributing to the educational improvement. Teacher effectiveness depends mainly on technological programmes specifically addressed to meet the needs and aspirations of the teacher. Danladi and Iorliam (2016) added that the qualities of a good teacher are quite obvious because of the role he is expected to play in the society. Anaso et al (2017) observed that education is the instrument for delivering a nation. Jibrin and Abdulhamid (2015) pointed out that education is a tool for scientific, technological, economic and political development of all nations. The *National Policy on Education* 2014 states that education is vital for socio-economic and political development, and maintained that it is the instrument par excellence for national development. The policy also indicated that without teacher education, no nation can rise above the quality of its teachers (FRN 2012, 2014). In view of the critical role that chemistry teachers play in the development of science and technology, efforts are being made to ensure that benefits of training and various programmes reach chemistry teachers in proportion to their numbers. For the purpose of this study, Information Communication Technology will be focused on.

The world is growing at a very fast rate with regard to Information Communication Technology (ICT) in science processes and methods (Kamar, Kubo and Ibrahim 2016). Abiola and Akanji (2016), Anaso, Haliru and Abdulkadir (2017) indicate that ICT is a set of technological tools and resources used in transmitting, storing, creating, sharing or exchanging information. The types of ICT in education include computers, the internet, and broadcasting technologies. Science is a dynamic human activity concerned with understanding the workings of the world. Muzaazi (2013) explained that the understanding obtained from science helps scientists to probe further into the nature of things and events, and to control and harness such things and events for the benefit of mankind. Chemistry as a branch of science deals with the study of matter, its structure, composition, properties, and the changes that it undergoes (Ojokuku, 2010). In other words, it involves the study of material substances that occur on the earth and in the universe. Chemistry serves as a major source of economic power in modern society especially in the manufacturing sector where new materials and household equipment have been made available to man. The uniqueness of chemistry and the central role it stands to play in the development of any nation are, however, not evident in the performance of students (Tambaya 2012). Thomas and Adebisi (2016) pointed out that the development of a nation starts through the impartation of knowledge acquired through education therefore, the use of ICT in science and in chemistry is a strong tool to equip the learners to learn objectively, curiously, and rationally. The use of information communication technology and e-learning will afford teachers and students much opportunity to discover information. The body of knowledge is value-oriented, goal-directed and purposive, which means that it has some inherent or inbuilt rewards and benefits both for the individual and the society at large. Technology has made the world to be a global place through information technology.

Teachers have a crucial role to play towards successful delivery of the education process. In addition, Udoh and Jacob (2016) reaffirm the central role of the teacher in the actualization of educational goals as well as ensuring the survival of the entire education system. The effectiveness of teachers depends mainly on technological programmes specifically addressed to meet their needs and aspirations. It is against this backdrop that this study was carried out to assess the level of development, provision and empowerment of chemistry teachers through ICT, as a technological programme.

Few studies seem to have investigated the socio-economic empowerment of chemistry teachers through Information Communication Technology (ICT) in the North West Zone. In view of the above, this study was conducted to assess the socio-economic empowerment of chemistry teachers in senior secondary schools in the use ICT skills and facilities in the North-West Zone of Nigeria.

Teachers are curriculum implementers and no one can give to students what they have not acquired therefore, the role of the chemistry teacher in using communication technology is critical. Akpan, Etiubon and Udosen (2017) reported that science teachers (chemistry in particular) need to be adequately prepared and empowered in diverse areas in order to develop appropriate skills in teaching and in the process, transfer same to the students. Wendy (2014) in Akpan, Etiubon and Udosen (2017) emphasized the use of regular objective and rigorous assessments to analyze the effectiveness of teachers' skills and preparedness, as these analysis facilitates STEM teachers' performance on learning outcomes particularly in evolving skills for socio-economic empowerment. It is against this background that this study was undertaken to assess the Socio-Economic Empowerment using Information Communication and Technology skills and facilities among secondary school chemistry teachers in North-West, Nigeria.

Objective of the study

The objective of the study is to:

1. Examine the provision and development of ICT facilities for empowering chemistry teachers in secondary schools.
2. Find out if chemistry teachers are empowered/skilled in the use of ICT facilities in secondary schools.

Research Questions

1. How frequent are ICT facilities developed and provided in secondary schools for use by chemistry teachers?
2. How effective are chemistry teachers empowered to use ICT facilities?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated to guide the study:

1. There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of chemistry teachers on the development and provision of ICT facilities for use in secondary schools.
2. There is no significant difference in the mean ratings on the empowerment of chemistry teachers through ICT facilities for use in secondary schools.

Methodology

The research design adopted the descriptive survey method. The decision to adopt the descriptive survey method was in line with Akuezuilo and Agu (2003) in Anaso (2017), who maintained that it is concerned with gathering information on people, thus the use of this research design.

The study population consisted of seven hundred and twenty (720) chemistry teachers drawn from eighty state government owned secondary schools in Kaduna and Kano States, selected through purposive random sampling technique. The sample size of the study was made up of one hundred and fifty (150) chemistry teachers from the two states (Kaduna and Kano). A total of one hundred and fifty (150) copies of the questionnaire was randomly distributed to the selected participants, however, only one hundred and twenty (120) copies of the questionnaire was dully filled and returned thus, the analysis for this study was based on the returned copies of the questionnaires. The sample therefore comprised of one hundred and twenty (120) chemistry teachers from seven hundred and twenty (720) secondary schools in two states (Kaduna and Kano).

Instrumentation

A structured questionnaire tagged “Chemistry Teachers Socio-Economic Empowerment Scale” (CTSEES) developed by the investigator was used. The questionnaire had two sections. Section 1 sought information on the development and provision of ICT facilities in secondary schools from the participants while Section 2 sought information on empowerment of chemistry teachers through ICT facility usage. It has a likert type questionnaire on a 4-point scale, ranging from; **Strongly disagree (SD) with (1point), Disagree (D) with (2points), Agreed (A) with 3points, Strongly agreed (SA) with (4points)**. Section A consists of 8 items while section B consists of 10 items.

Validity and Reliability

Two computer and two chemistry experts from Department of Science Education, Ahmadu Bello University Zaria, and face validated the instrument. The reliability of the instrument was 0.79. The teachers responses on the development and provision of ICT for chemistry teaching and empowerment of chemistry teachers through the use of ICT facilities, was scored in means and standard deviation as presented in Tables 1 and 2. Decisions on agreement were based on midpoint of 2.50 and above, while mean score of 2.49 and below implied disagreement for each of the items and variables. Mean was used in answering the research questions and one sample t-test was used in testing the hypotheses.

Presentation of Results

The results of the study are presented in terms of research questions and hypotheses respectively as shown in Tables 1 to 6.

Research Question 1

How frequent are ICT facilities developed and provided in secondary schools for use by chemistry teachers?

Table 1: Responses of chemistry teachers on the development and provision of ICT for chemistry instruction

Items	SD(1)	D(2)	A(3)	SA(4)	Total	Mean
The school has well developed ICT facility for teaching chemistry.	18 (18)	60 (120)	12 (36)	30 (120)	294	2.45
ICT is a new approach for teaching chemistry	12 (12)	40 (80)	28 (84)	38 (152)	328	2.77
ICT facilities are very expensive to procure and maintained	16 (16)	24 (48)	60 (180)	20 (80)	324	2.70
Has ventilated computer room	40 (40)	30 (60)	44 (132)	6 (24)	256	2.13

Has qualified chemistry teachers who are computer literate	30 (30)	50 (100)	30 (90)	10 (40)	260	2.16
Has overhead projector to facilitate learning	52 (52)	34 (68)	24 (72)	10 (80)	232	1.93
Inadequate funding affects the use of ICT services	20 (20)	10 (20)	40 (120)	30 (120)	280	2.33
ICT facilities are adequate to cater for the number of students	30 (30)	70 (140)	10 (30)	10 (40)	240	2.00

TAWR 2.34

Analysis from Table 1 shows chemistry teachers' response on the development and provision of ICT facilities for the teaching and learning of chemistry in two states (Kaduna and Kano). Respondents agreed with items number 2, 3, and 7 with mean values of 2.77, 2.70, and 2.33. They disagreed with items number 1, 4, 5, 6, and 8 with mean values of 2.45, 2.13, 2.16, 1.93, and 2.0 respectively. The Total Weighted Average Response of 2.34 falls below 2.5 and this indicated a below average proficiency in integrating ICT instruction.

Research Question 2

How effective are chemistry teachers empowered to use ICT facilities?

Table 2: Responses of chemistry teachers on the empowerment to use ICT for chemistry instruction

Item Statement	SD(1)	D(2)	A(3)	SA(4)	Total	Mean
Chemistry teachers cannot afford ICT tools such as laptops, desktops, projectors, modem etc.	8 (8)	32 (64)	64 (192)	16 (32)	328	2.73
Most chemistry teachers are not knowledgeable in ICT applications	22 (22)	30 (60)	52 (156)	16 (64)	302	2.52
The government and school management show nonchalant attitude in training chemistry teachers to get abreast of ICT.	24 (24)	20 (40)	64 (192)	12 (48)	304	2.53
Most chemistry teachers cannot afford to subscribe to the internet and ICT services	26 (26)	18 (36)	56 (168)	20 (80)	310	2.60
Lack ICT facilities to support active teaching of chemistry at the secondary school level.	18 (18)	30 (60)	64 (192)	8 (32)	302	2.52
Lack of access to research findings on Information Communication Technology.	20 (20)	30 (60)	60 (180)	10 (40)	300	2.50
Lack of funds to schools by the government on ICT applications.	30 (30)	10 (20)	56 (120)	24 (96)	314	2.62
Chemistry teachers participate in workshops related to ICT	60 (60)	30 (60)	22 (66)	8 (32)	218	1.83
Chemistry teachers have much time to prepare and implement ICT in their teaching	22 (22)	41 (82)	51 (153)	6 (24)	281	2.34
Chemistry teachers are encouraged to use ICT facilities.	60 (60)	36 (72)	20 (60)	4 (16)	208	1.73

TAWR 2.31

Analysis from Table 2 shows response on empowerment of chemistry teachers and the use of ICT facilities in secondary schools. Respondents agreed with items number 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, and 7 with mean values of 2.73, 2.52, 2.53, 2.60, 2.52, 2.50, and 2.62 respectively. They disagreed with items number 8, 9, and 10 with mean 1.83, 2.34, and 1.73 respectively. The Total weighted Average Response of 2.31 is below 2.50. This means that chemistry teachers were not empowered on the use of ICT facilities (use of multimedia) in teaching chemistry.

Testing of Ho1: There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of chemistry teachers on the development and provision of ICT facilities for use in secondary schools.

One –sample t-test was used. This was based on the fact that it was the main statistical tool that can help to determine significant difference between an observed mean and a constant, thus establishing the significance of the expressed responses of the respondents on the developmental effects of ICT/Multimedia presentation examined in the study. The summary of the result of the test is presented in table 3.

Table 3: One sample statistics on development of ICT in secondary schools understudy

Variables	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Development				
ICT	120	17.7541	4.72107	.60447
Constant	120			

The result in Table 3 shows the level of responses on the items on development of ICT in secondary schools. They had a mean score of 17.7541 with a standard deviation of 4.72107 and the standard error was .60447

Table 4: One sample t-test on development of ICT in secondary schools understudy

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	Df	t-cal	T critical	P
Development								
ICT	120	17.7541	4.72107	.60447.	119	29.371	1.96	0.000

The result in Table 4 revealed that significant differences exist in the level of responses on the items of respondents on development of ICT in secondary schools. Reasons being that the calculated t- value of 29.371 is greater than the t- critical of 1.96. The obtained p value of 0.000 is lower than the 0.05 alpha level of significance set for the study. The hypothesis is therefore rejected since there is significant difference in the mean ratings of chemistry teachers on the development and provision of ICT facilities for use in secondary schools.

Testing of Ho2: There is no significant difference in the mean ratings on the empowerment of chemistry teachers through ICT facilities for use in secondary schools.

Table 5: One sample t-test Statistics on empowerment of chemistry teachers through ICT (multimedia)

Variable	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Empowerment	120	42.9836	6.85199	.87731
Constant	120			

The result in Table 5 shows the level of responses on empowerment of teachers on ICT in secondary schools. They had a mean score of 42.9836 with a standard deviation of 6.85199 while the Standard Error Mean was .87731.

Table 6: One sample t-test on empowerment of chemistry teachers through ICT (multimedia)

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	Df	t	T critical	P
Development of ICT	120	42.9836	16.85199	.87731.	119	48.995	1.96	0.000

The result in Table 6 revealed that the calculated t-value of 48.995 is greater than the critical t- value of 1.96. P-value of 0.000 was obtained at 0.05 level of significance and 119 degree of freedom. Significant differences exist in the level of responses on empowerment of chemistry teachers through ICT (multimedia). The null hypothesis is rejected. Thus there is significant difference in the mean ratings on the empowerment of chemistry teachers through ICT facilities and their usage in secondary schools.

Discussion of Findings

The findings of the study revealed that the provision and the development of Information Communication Technology facilities for chemistry teachers were viewed as a new approach to teaching. In addition, the schools had qualified chemistry teachers who were computer literate but had no overhead projector for learning. Also, the Information Communication Technology facilities were poorly maintained due to inadequate funding. Chemistry teachers attested to the fact that ICT facilities were neither developed nor adequate to cater for the growing population of students in the two states. It could therefore be inferred from this study that ICT facilities have not contributed significantly to the literacy skills of chemistry teachers in the states under study. The respondents agreed that chemistry teachers could not afford ICT tools such as laptops, desktops, projectors and were not knowledgeable in ICT application. They could not afford to subscribe to the internet and ICT services nor participate in workshops related to ICT. They also indicated that they had no time to prepare and implement ICT in their teachings nor were they encouraged to use ICT facilities. From the findings, the government and school management showed a nonchalant attitude to training of chemistry teachers on ICT and could not fund ICT applications in the various schools. This brings about poor development of a nation and this is in line with the findings of Olomukoro (2016), who maintained that the rate of development of a nation is related to its investment in human and non-human resources. The provision of ICT facilities will equip chemistry teachers with the right type of skills necessary for industrial development and economic growth. The result from Tables 3 to 6 indicated a significant difference in the mean ratings of the chemistry teachers on CTSEES and showed that chemistry teachers were not empowered to use ICT facilities (use of multimedia presentation) in teaching chemistry at the secondary school level.

The present study is therefore significant, in that it has provided an empirical base for the development and empowerment of chemistry teachers through ICT facilities. The human capital theory is relevant to this study because emphasis is laid on the investment of people through educational and technological activities for skills acquisition. This will ultimately lead to capacity building and empowerment through skill utilisation. The findings from this study tallies with Olomukoro (2012) in her study on influence of literacy education programmes on socio-economic and psychological empowerment of women in Edo and Delta States, Nigeria, indicated that without investing in human capital, skills will not be acquired and there cannot be self-development and improved socio-economic status.

Conclusion

The study has established a strong relationship between ICT and socio-economic empowerment of chemistry teachers in the area investigated. Poor development and provision of ICT facilities are some of the challenges facing its optimal usage. There is need, therefore, to deliberately empower chemistry teachers with skills and knowledge through ICT programmes. Access to ICT programmes could improve the socio-economic empowerment of chemistry teachers in any given nation.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following recommendations are made:

1. Policy-makers should ensure that functional ICT programmes are incorporated into the curriculum to help chemistry teachers actualize their potentials. Skill acquisition is the best option for empowerment of chemistry teachers at the secondary school level.
2. Ministry of Education should promote literacy on ICT facilities by organizing seminars and workshops for chemistry teachers.
3. The state government and school management should be more proactive in funding ICT projects, which involves providing functional standard computers and adequate gadgets
4. Monitoring bodies should monitor the provision, development and usage of ICT facilities (computers, multimedia gadgets, etc.) in schools by daily checks. This is to ensure that the facilities are used by the teachers and students.
5. Chemistry teachers should be encouraged to use ICT facilities in their teaching.
6. The state governments should provide and develop adequate ICT facilities to cater for chemistry teachers and the growing number of students in the states.

References

- Abiola, Y.F. & Akanji, C.O (2016) Attitude of Teachers towards Information Communication Technology in Lagos State. 57th Annual Conference Proceedings, 2016. Pp33-35

- Akpan, A. O., Etiubon, R. U. & Udosen, I. N. (2017) STEM Teachers' Preparedness for Socio-Economic Empowerment of Senior Secondary Science Students in Nigeria. *Science Teachers Association of Nigeria* 2017 Conference Proceedings, Pg37-41
- Anaso J. N., Musa H. & Abdukadir .A. (2017) Assessment of Multimedia Presentations in Chemical Equilibrium a Determinant of Achievement among Secondary School Chemistry Students In North West, Nigeria. *International Journal of Innovative Research and Advanced Studies (IJIRAS)* Volume 4 Issue 8, August www.ijiras.com
- Danladi, N.E. & Lorliam (2016) Challenges of Implementing Cultural Compliments of Curriculum by Teachers in Junior Secondary Schools in Nigeria. *Journal of Educational Research and Development*. 10(1) 106-115
- Federal Ministry of Education (2012) *4-year strategy plan for the development of the education sector*, Abuja. Federal Government Press.
- Federal Ministry of Education (2014) *National Policy on Education*. 6th Ed). Lagos NERDC. Press.
- Jibrin, A,G & Abdulhamid, A (2015) Effects of Problem- Solving Strategy and Gender on Academic Achievement of Pre-Service Teachers in Genetic for Functional skills Acquisition. *International Journal of Research in Science, Technology and Mathematics Education*. 3(2) 47-48
- Kamar, Y.M, Kubo, G.B & Ibrahim, R. (2016). Emerging Communication Technologies in Science Education and Existing Issues of E.Compliance among Science Teachers in Nigeria. *57th Annual Conference Proceedings*, 2016. Pp3-9
- Muzaazi A.O. (2013) Roles of Science in Modern Development. *International Journal of Education, Science, Humanities, Mathematics and Studies* 5 (1&2) 85-93
- Ojokuku G. O. (2010) *Understanding Chemistry for Senior Secondary Schools*. Published by Press on Chembooks.
- Olomukoro, O.C. (2012). Influence of Literacy Education Programmes on Socio-Economic and Psychological Empowerment of Women in Edo and Delta States, Nigeria. (Unpublished PhD Dissertation. Faculty of Education, University of Ibadan).
- Olomukoro, O.C. (2016) Socio-Economic Empowerment of Women through Literacy Education Programmes in Edo and Delta States, Nigeria. *Journal of Educational Research and Development*. 10(1) 172-185
- Oxford Dictionary Current English (2022) Tenth edition.
- Tambaya, I.S. (2012). Effect of Teacher –Student Verbal Interaction on Student's Academic Achievement in Some Biology Concepts of Senior Secondary School Students in Sabon Gari Local Government Area, Zaria. *Journal of Studies in Science and Mathematics Education*. 2(1) 24-28
- Thomas, A.A. & Adebisi, R.O. (2016) Utilization of E- Learning Technologies in Teaching and Learning Science in Senior Secondary Schools. *57th Annual Conference Proceedings*, 2016 pp. 50-58
- Rahman A. (2013) Women's Empowerment; Concept and Beyond. *Global Journal of Human Social Science, Sociology and Culture*. 13(6) 9-13
- Udoh, A.O. & Jacob, S.S. (2016) Evaluation of Universal Basic Education Programme in Eket Senatorial District of Akwa Ibom State, *Science Teachers Association of Nigeria 57th Annual Conference Proceedings*, 2016